

TITLES OF RULERS OF THE HELLENISTIC PERIOD

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ABSTRACT

This article describes an analysis of the titles of rulers in the history of the statehood of Ancient Central Asia. An analysis of the epigraphic data reveals that in the city-states of Central Asia, the functions of religious and secular authority were gradually merged into the hands of a single ruler. Thus, the rulers of Central Asia assumed the positions of military chief, chief judge, and leading priest. In time, various titles were combined to form the title of "Ruler of the four countries of the world." The article covers the history of the emergence and evolution of titles in the history of the statehood of Ancient Central Asia.

The study of the history of state titles is one of the most relevant scientific fields in world history, which begins directly with the history of Mesopotamian statehood. The titles "en" and "ensi" are the origin of titles.

In the history of Uzbekistan, this issue has not been studied as a separate topic, especially for the periods of the formation of the first statehood, the issue of titles in the early period of the Uzbek statehood has not been studied at all by historians due to the lack of sources or research, and not approaching scientifically to the sources. Because of independence, a wide way has been opened to study the centuries-old history, scientific, cultural and spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people, and also for using it as an invaluable property of the nation. The history plays important role in

consolidating and developing this spiritual and ideological basis.

Nowadays, although significant scientific progress has been achieved in the history research of statehood, which began in the second half of the 19th century, [Азамат Зиё. –Т., 2000; Ртвеладзе В.; Саидов А.Х., Абдуллаев Е.В.– Т. 2001;], the early forms of statehood, the emergence of the management system, the issues of titles and positions have not been fully resolved. The scientists such as E.V. Rtveldadze, V.A.Livshits, B.I.Weinberg, I.M.Dyakonov, E.V.Zeymal, S.P. Tolstov, O.I. Smirnova, V.B. Henning, G'.Boboyorov considerably conducted scientific research about the main features of ancient history and the emergence of state titles by researchers. However, although the emergence, ethnic origin, and content of the titles of some states, such as the rulers of Khorezm and

Kushan Empires, have been well studied, the scientific research has not been conducted on the titles and chronological period of the rulers of states that emerged after the Arab invasion.

MAIN PART.

Numismatic sources also showed the name of the state, the territory occupied by the state, the name of the ruler, the title he received, the image of the ruler, the time of his accession to the throne and the years of his reign. That is why we study coins as a small source. But, when it comes to details, it is better than others in objectivity and scientificity.

The analysis of the data shows that the changing of the titles of the rulers of Central Asia due to the language, cultural and historical reasons of countries is a historically regular process. The lack of information can make studying these titles difficult. The titles of Hellenistic period are mostly studied through numismatic sources. Explaining the titles of rulers through numismatic sources is important, also, it gives opportunity to deeply study main theories about the evolution and the emergence of titles in Uzbekistan.

The word numismatics comes from the Greek "Nomisma" which means coin or small copper coin. Avers - the front side of the coin, reverse - the back of the coin, element - the person who minted the coin (ruler), and the legend means the inscription on the coin. [М, Издательство МГУ, 1990 г].

According to the history of Central Asian numismatics, the expression of titles and the image of the ruler on coins dates back to the time of Alexander the Great. For the first time, he minted the image and titles of the king and the gods on the coins [Ртвеладзе Э.В. Ташкент. 1987.-С-10].

After the death of Alexander the Great, the state he founded was divided into three parts, namely Macedonia, Egypt and Babylon (Seleukia). Diadochs - his generals ruled these states. The power of the generals with the title of Diadox was limited by the king. The southern regions of Central Asia became part of the Seleucid Empire founded by Seleucus I "Nicator" (conqueror, savior). Seleucus I received the title "Nicator". Seleucus I declared his title "victor" (nicator) after winning the fight between the diadoches. The kings of the Seleucid dynasty had different titles, for example, Antiochus IV "Epiphanes", Demetrius II "Soter" (savior). These titles appeared first on royal coins and later in written sources.

The appearance of the first coins minted in Bactria is associated with the name of Seleucus' son Antiochus I. The names of these coins were also different. For example, gold coins were called staters, and silver coins were called tetradrachms, drachmas and half-drachmas. [Ртвеладзе Э.В. 1987г.С-10.]

The image of crowned king was minted in the right side of Antioch I's coins. On the reverse, there is an image of Zeus without clothes. Zeus holding a shield and the Greek title "Vasilevs Antiochoi" which means "King Antiochus" were written. [Беляева Т. 1978- С-54.].

In Samarkand Sogd of the end of the 3rd century - the beginning of the 2nd century BC, the texts on the coins issued in imitation of the coins of Antioch were written in Aramaic script along with Greek script. On the coins, the king's name and title are not written in Sughd script, but in the Aramaic MR`Y (meaning lord, ruler). A second title appearing on the coins is also written in Aramaic, MLK (high-ranking,

king). [Э.В. Ртвеладзе, А.Х.Хасанов,Е.Б.Абдуллаев. 2001. С-104].

We can see that Greco-Bactrian coins are mostly in the same pattern, on the right side, the image of the ruler, his rank, name and title are written in Greek in a circle or column. On the reverse side, the image of the gods that the ruler was attracted to, for example, Zeus, Heracles, Poseidon, Apollo, Dioscuri, was depicted. [Ртвеладзе Э.В. 1987. С-10.]. In them, the rank, name and nickname of the king are placed in the form of a semicircle or a column, for example, the Greek title "podalo Antimachus of the god". In addition, on the reverse side of the coin, next to the image of the god, there is a monogram consisting of several Greek letters (monogram in Greek is mono - one; grama-letter). A monogram on a coin is an initial of the master or ruler who minted the coin.

Diodotus, the founder of the Greco-Bactrian state, was described as "the ruler of a thousand Bactrian cities" by Greek-Roman historians Pompey Trogus and Augustine. Diodos I minted silver coins, and his identity as the founder and legitimate king of this state can be seen from the coins he minted. His portrait was depicted on the coins, and "King Antiochus" (Vasilevs Antiochoi) was written. From the beginning of his reign, he minted the name of Antiochus, not his name, on coins. He did not write his name until the end of his life. The reverse of the coins depicted Zeus holding a shield and an eagle. The meaning of this is that Diodotus and his ancestors were patronized by Zeus. The translation of the name "Diodod" from Greek also means "given by God". [Казим Абдуллаев, Амридин Бердимуратов. 2010.С-112].

The fact that Diadotus received the titles "Soter" (savior) and "Theos" (god) can be seen from the coins minted by Agathocles in honor of Diodotus. On the coin minted by the Greek-Bactrian ruler Diodotus II, Zeus was depicted holding a shield and the title "Basilevs Diodotois" (King Diodotus) was written on the coin. Diodos II mints his own name on coins, unlike his father Diodos I.

Another ruler of this country, Antimachus minted his coins, equating himself to the gods, and minted coins with the inscription "Basileus Antimachus Theos", that is, "King Antimachus is a God". It can be seen from this, through equating his title to god and making divine, we can know that the religion is important in state system. Having great importance of religion in the Hellenistic states was reflected in the process of studying coins that minted in ancient states.

On Greco-Bactrian coins, there are also cases of deviations from the standard images. The image of king and the title "The Great King Eucratides" was written in the right side of the coins that minted in the reign of King Eucratides, while the reverse side shows a young man or woman with a gold crown on her forehead. At the bottom of the photo is written: "Heleocles and Laodice".[3].

In Sh.Pidaev's book "Ancient Termiz" gives the following information about the coins of the Greco-Bactrian kings: The images on the coins of the Greco-Bactrian kings are depicted with great skill. These coins are brilliant examples of medalist art. It confirms that the title "King Euthydemus the Ruler" was depicted in the coin of King Euthydemus.

On the right side of the coins minted by Euthydemus is the head image of

Herakles with a beard and mustache, on the reverse is a galloping horse and the title "Horn Euthydemus" (Vasilevs Euthydemoy). The well-known numismatist A. Hening describes the Aramaic inscription MR'Y on the tetradrachms of Euthydemus as MRAY as a title given to hierarchical rulers who are considered lower than the king. [Ртвеладзе Э.В.2009 й.С-346].

On the avers side of the coins minted by the order of Demetrius, the image of the king, wearing an elephant-shaped helmet with long tusks, carrying his trunk over his head, is depicted.

The reverse side of the coin depicts the image of Zeus holding a crown in his right hand, a lion's skin in his left hand and the title "King Demetrius" (Vasilevs Demetrius) written in Greek. After Demetrius conquered North India, Greco-Bactrian coins also appear with kharoshtxi inscriptions and animal images. In addition, the title INDORIUM (ruler of Indian possessions) is expressed in written sources.

On the right side of the Eucratides coin is the image of the king wearing a Macedonian helmet, and on the reverse is the image of the twin brothers Dioscuri on horseback, and on the coin he expressed his title through the Greek inscription "Sovereign king Eucratides" (Soter vasilevs Evkratidoi).

It is known from the coins he minted that his title was Soter. Eucratides defeated Demetrius in the struggle for the throne. After gaining power, he took the title "Soter" (savior). This title was used for that he saved Bactria from Demetrius. [Попов А.А. 2001г.С-54].

There are written and numismatic sources confirming that Bactrian language and Greek script, Brahmi and Khoroshtkhi scripts were also used in ancient Bactria during the time of Demetrius and Eucratides. [Асқаров А.А.2015й. С-187].

The ancient Greek historian Arrian mentioned in his work that the commander of the Bactrian army was called "Fruararch". It is known from written sources that the prime minister was called Vazork fromodar.

To sum up, Diodotus, the ruler of the Greco-Bactrian state, initially remained loyal to the Seleucid ruler Seleucids, minting his coins in honor of Antiochus I, which was a symbol of state independence. By the time of his successors, they carried titles such as "Soter", "Theos", "Vasilevs", "Vasilevs Vasileon". The rulers of the Davan state are mentioned in Chinese sources with the title "Wan" (king). Also, the fact that the rulers of Khorezm minted coins with the same dynastic stamp for seven centuries was a rare event even in world history.

CONCLUSION.

Numismatics, which has its importance among the supportive fields of history, gained its prestige after the independence of our country and gained the status of an independent historical science. Because the role of numismatics in studying our history is incomparable. Coins provide us with valuable information about political, economic, religious worldviews of nations, titles of rulers, in addition to historical and cultural events from BC to the present day.

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